

Enhancing The Resilience of a Critical Building Through the Optimization of Food, Energy, and Water Systems

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Abstract In the current landscape, most buildings lack the ability to endure and function effectively during and after disasters. The insufficient preparedness of critical building facilities leads to disruptions in their operations for specific durations, emphasizing the urgent need for research and the integration of strategies to enhance building resilience. Existing research on a comprehensive approach addressing the resilience of buildings concerning food, energy, water, and structural systems is limited. Addressing this gap, the paper focuses on identifying and proposing strategies to enhance buildings' resilience in terms of their Food, Energy, and Water (FEW) systems, especially in critical facilities such as primary health centres. The study centers around a primary health center in the flood-prone suburbs of Chennai, India, a city facing significant challenges, including flooding, earthquakes, cyclones, and tsunamis. This research encompasses vulnerability analysis and proposes mitigation strategies such as On-site renewable energy production (solar), critical energy storage system, rainwater harvesting, critical water storage system, on-site food production, and edible landscaping along with passive design techniques to improve the resilience of the building in terms of energy, water, and food. Subsequent to the deployment of these strategic measures, a meticulous assessment of their efficacy ensues, days of autonomy of 9.5, 17, and 3 days for Food, Energy, and Water, respectively. This outcome is intricately aligned with the established standards of the RELi rating system, specifically pertaining to the critical infrastructure of the building. This study provides valuable insights into enhancing building resilience and serves as a practical model for architects and builders facing similar challenges in the contemporary context, offering innovative solutions for disaster-prone regions.

Keywords Resilience, FEW Systems, Critical infrastructure.

Introduction

Buildings play an important role in the sustainability and well-being of a community. They ensure the continuity of essential services and the safety of occupants. With the current scenarios of climate change causing flash floods and rapid changes in conditions, it is imperative to explore innovative strategies to fortify the resilience of critical buildings. The research paper aims to address this imperative through a multifaceted approach to enhance the resilience of a critical building. Specifically, the paper's focus revolves around the optimization of food, energy, and water (FEW) systems. The study aims to provide insights into the practical implementation of resilience-enhancing measures through a base case study. The paper aspires to contribute to the development of sustainable and adaptable critical buildings that can withstand emerging climatic challenges.

Objective

To propose an ideal resilient design module for a primary health care unit that can be followed in disaster-prone areas to adapt to prevailing situations during the vulnerable period, utilizing RELi benchmarks across water, energy, food, and environmental efficiency categories.

Need

Enhancing the emergency preparedness, sustainability, and community well-being of primary healthcare systems is essential (Uscher et.al., 2013). Particularly during disasters, ensuring the operational continuity of critical infrastructures such as hospitals is pivotal for addressing the health needs of affected citizens. A comprehensive understanding of the interdependencies among resources is essential to identify vulnerabilities and formulate strategies to effectively mitigate the impact of disasters. The introduction of innovative practices within healthcare systems holds the potential to empower professionals in responding adeptly to challenges pertaining to food, energy, and water, thereby fostering the development of adaptable healthcare systems. As highlighted by Mala Rao and Eva Pilot (2014), research has demonstrated that the availability of primary care services significantly enhances patients' self-perceived health status, further emphasizing the need for comprehensive exploration into the benefits of primary care in disaster-prone areas.

Materials and Method

Literature Review

Food security. The manifestation of food and nutritional challenges in the aftermath of a disaster is contingent upon various factors, including the nature of the disaster, its duration, the geographical extent of the affected area, and the nutritional state of the population before the calamity strikes. While earthquakes typically exert minimal impact on long-

term food supplies, events such as hurricanes, floods, and tsunamis directly impinge on food availability by causing widespread damage to crops, livestock, and stored food resources. Disasters, by their very nature, disrupt transportation systems, communication channels, and social and economic routines, leading to scenarios akin to the Chennai floods of 2015 and 2023, where inundation and isolation hindered access to food supplies during and after cyclonic events. Thus, the mere existence of food stores is insufficient; ensuring population access becomes paramount. The required quantification of food aid necessitates understanding the daily caloric needs per person. According to Matthew Solan (2023), women aged 19 to 50 should target 1,800 to 2,000 daily calories, with those aged 51 and older requiring 1,600 calories. Meanwhile, men aged 19 to 50 should aim for 2,200 to 2,400 calories, and those aged 51 and older require 2,000 calories. Considering the variable number of people utilizing the facility, contingent on its size and discernible from an analysis of the previous year's demographic patterns, the facility should be equipped to provide food aid for its users over a span of 3-4 days in the event of a disaster.

Water supply As elucidated by Cassivi et al. (2022), empirical investigations reveal that within the Japanese context, a supplementary water tank endowed with a storage capacity of approximately 8.32 liters per square meter emerges as a viable means to sustain a healthcare facility for a duration of about one day. Within the expansive ambit of larger Japanese university facilities accommodating 650–800 beds, the strategic deployment of either a sizable water reservoir, exemplified by a 700 m³ tank, or the adoption of dual water tanks, each boasting a volumetric capacity of 160 m³, facilitates a supply adequate for approximately one day. This calculation duly incorporates an estimated daily consumption ranging between 500–600 m³, particularly during the peak weekdays. Turning attention to the daily water consumption dynamics in Chennai, the World Health Organization (WHO) prescribes a per capita daily water allocation of 135 liters for denizens dwelling in urban locales. However, given prevailing circumstances and attendant modifications, the actualized daily water supply dwindles significantly to 65 liters. Delving deeper into this discourse, Vikaspedia (2023) expounds that health facilities with a bed capacity of fewer than 100 necessitate a daily water requirement hovering around 350 liters per bed. In stark contrast, hospitals endowed with more than 100 beds demand an augmented water allocation of approximately 400 liters per bed per day. These numerical representations underscore the pivotal significance of meticulous water management considerations, particularly within healthcare settings, underscoring their indispensable role in fortifying effective disaster preparedness and judicious resource allocation.

Energy requirements. Primary health care services demand uninterrupted access to a 24/7 power source, crucial for the continuous operation of essential equipment like refrigerators, nebulizers, and lighting facilities. In addressing this imperative, IIEC (2022) is committed to ensuring the round-the-clock functionality of Primary Health Centers (PHCs) by implementing solar PV systems and providing refrigerators specifically designed for storing vaccines and life-saving medicines. This strategic initiative is designed to enhance the delivery of healthcare services, with a particular emphasis on benefiting communities, especially women and children.

The advantages associated with harnessing clean energy sources for 24/7 electricity provision in PHCs are noteworthy. This approach not only facilitates an increase in the number of patients served but also extends the operational hours of the PHCs. Moreover, there is a substantial enhancement, ranging from 120% to 150%, in the coverage of diseases being treated. The implementation of solar PV systems contributes to overall preparedness, ensuring that health centers are equipped to handle diverse medical needs efficiently. Importantly, reliance on clean energy mitigates the risk of accidents caused by unexpected power cuts, underscoring the safety and reliability of such a power solution in the healthcare setting. This comprehensive strategy aligns with the overarching goal of IIEC (2022) to optimize healthcare services and contribute to the well-being of diverse communities.

Methodology

To address the need for enhancing the resilience of critical buildings, especially those that are crucial, this paper begins by identifying various requirements and implementing an integrated approach to strategies that improve a building's resilience in terms of Food, Water, and Energy. To assess the outcomes of these strategies, a primary health center, located in the suburbs of Chennai, an Indian city vulnerable to major disasters, is considered for the study. After analyzing and implementing strategies through FEW systems in the case that was taken, a comparative analysis between the base case scenario and the design case is conducted to understand the overall impact of the approach to attain resilience (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Methodology

Benchmarks

RELi rating is a sustainability and resilience rating system developed by The Institute for Market Transformation to Sustainability. RELi is designed to assess and enhance the resilience of buildings and communities in the face of natural and man-made disasters, climate change, and other disruptions. Within the overarching framework of RELi standards, a systematic and structured approach necessitates the integration of strategies that can be methodically classified into four pivotal domains. These include Integrated Water Resilience, wherein comprehensive planning and implementation strategies are employed to enhance water security, efficiency, and resilience against potential disruptions such as floods or droughts. Sustainable Energy Practices constitute another vital domain, emphasizing the adoption of renewable energy sources, energy efficiency measures, and resilient energy systems to ensure a reliable and sustainable power supply, even in adverse conditions. The domain of Integrated Urban Food Systems prioritizes the development of resilient and sustainable food production, distribution, and consumption systems within urban environments, thereby promoting local food security and concurrently reducing environmental impacts. Lastly, Reduced Environmental Impact encompasses measures geared towards minimizing the ecological footprint of buildings and communities, entailing sustainable site development, biodiversity conservation, and waste reduction. Aligned with these foundational categories, a meticulous examination of various strategies from the RELi framework is diligently undertaken and purposefully integrated into the design case. This not only signifies a steadfast commitment to meeting the stringent standards set by RELi but also underscores a holistic approach aimed at enhancing the overall resilience, sustainability, and environmental performance of the designed structure. The strategic incorporation of these diverse strategies fortifies the resulting design, enabling it to adeptly navigate and adapt to a spectrum of challenges, thereby contributing substantially to the creation of more resilient and sustainable built environments.

Site Identification

Indian cities, including Chennai, are increasingly susceptible to disasters exacerbated by factors such as climate change and global warming. Among these cities, Chennai stands out as particularly vulnerable to various disasters, including cyclones, floods, and earthquake-induced tsunamis. The aftermath of such disasters, especially in suburban and rural areas, often witnesses relief efforts unfolding at a slower pace, underscoring an urgent need to fortify critical buildings in these regions. One such critical building, a primary health center, located in the southern suburbs of Chennai in Medavakkam, Tambaram taluk, Chengalpattu district, Tamil Nadu, has been singled out for a comprehensive study. The site details reveal a area of 5000 sqm, with a roof area of 1160 sqm, hardscape area of 716 sqm, and softscape area of 3124 sqm (Fig. 2). The health center accommodates 28 beds, crucial for providing essential healthcare services during and after disasters. Considering the average annual rainfall in Chennai stands at 1400mm, this study focuses on the specific vulnerabilities and resilience requirements of this primary health center to enhance its capacity to effectively respond to and recover from disasters.

Fig. 2. Site Plan

Results and Discussion

Vulnerability Analysis

Chennai is prone to cyclones originating in the Bay of Bengal, during the northeast monsoon season. This brings heavy rainfall, strong winds, and storm surges that lead to floods and infrastructure damage. The city experiences periodic floods that are exacerbated by rapid urbanization and inadequate drainage systems. Chennai faces heatwaves, during the summer months with high temperature and humidity levels. Prolonged exposure to extreme heat poses health risks. The condition also strains the energy resources for cooling systems. During this period water shortage also can be experienced because of the over-extraction of groundwater, and inadequate water management practices. Urbanization and industrial activities cause air pollution, which affects the respiratory health of the population. Poor air quality escalated health issues during extreme climatic events. These disasters cause other difficulties for people in their daily lives. Transportation gets disrupted when roads and systems get submerged under floodwaters. This disrupts daily commutes, hindering access to one's daily routine. Power outages can be commonly observed during an event of flood, this hampers the operation of water pumping stations, hospitals, and other critical infrastructure. The submerged roads are a challenge for swift and organized evacuation. The supply chains are disrupted which leads to a shortage of essential supplies like food, medicine, and fuel. Even accessing grocery stores, pharmacies, and other essentials is burdened.

Implementation

Upon scrutinizing the foundational requisites of the base case, a series of strategies geared toward enhancing the resilience of the building concerning its FEW systems are systematically instituted and appraised within the framework of the design case. These strategies are discerned in accordance with the cardinal principles of Reduction, Reuse/Recycle, and Renewal. It is imperative to underscore that the primacy is accorded to the reduction of demand, signifying a deliberate prioritization of curbing resource requirements before delving into the exploration of alternative strategies.

Water Upon meticulously examining strategies for mitigating indoor water consumption, the retrofit measure incorporating low flow fixtures emerges as a discerned solution. Simultaneously, the curtailment of outdoor water utilization is contemplated through the implementation of an efficient landscape design strategy, featuring the integration of native plants and xeriscaping principles. Furthermore, the sustainability paradigm is further enriched by identifying strategies falling under the ambit of Recycle/Reuse, namely rainwater harvesting and greywater recycling, thereby underscoring a comprehensive approach to water resource management within the designated framework.

Base case The recognized PHC manifests a requisition for water across four distinct categories, encompassing exigencies such as general hospital needs, domestic usage, flushing demand, and the irrigation water essential for landscape maintenance. Synthesizing these elements, the aggregate water demand crystallizes at a substantial 18,797.5 Kl (kilolitres) annually. This quantification underscores the multifaceted nature of water utilization within the PHC, reflecting the diverse and vital functions necessitating a comprehensive and judicious water management strategy.

Rainwater harvesting Mohammed, T. A. et al (2007) stated that it is preferable to integrate the rainwater harvesting systems with the existing conventional water supply systems, which will help to meet the increasing demand for water supply and contribute to the sustainability of the water supply. In this design case, rainwater harvesting with an efficiency of 80% gives an amount of 2,200.8 Kl per Year (Table 1), which can be used for irrigation of vegetation or can be filtered and used for domestic purposes during disaster times. Stormwater drains collect the water from the pavement that circulates water through slopes using gravity. A combination of meshes and gutter guards are used to remove larger contamination from the water collected from pavement; sedimentation and gravity filtration are further used as secondary filtration. As stated by Muthukumar, M. (2022), rhizo-filtration is used in the landscape area to filter the impurities. The collected water can be used for irrigation and cleaning purposes.

Table 1. Rainwater Harvesting Calculation

	Rainfall in m	Runoff Coefficient	Surface Area	Efficiency of harvesting	Total Litres/Year
Roof	1.4	0.9	1160	0.8	1169280
Pavement	1.4	0.85	716	0.8	681632
Landscape	1.4	0.1	3124	0.8	349888
Total Rainwater Harvested					2200800

Low Flow Fixtures. Water sensor devices that can be incorporated in sinks, faucets, and other bathroom fixtures reduce the water flow rate by 30% less than the standard flow rate, states Jain, M. S. (2023). After incorporating these low-flow fixtures for flushing and domestic purpose appliances, 36.85% (1,280.464 Kl per year) water reduction is seen from the base case (Table 2).

Table 2. Water Demand Reduction Calculation (Design Case - using Low flow Fixtures)

	Reduction		Base Case Demand (in litres)	Reduced amount of water /Year	Water Demand After Reduction/Year
Tap Aerators (Flushing Demand)	50%	0.5	1216180	608090	608090
Sensors (Domestic Use)	30%	0.3	2241246	672373.8	1568872.2
Total Amount of Water Reduced				1280463.8	

Greywater recycling Liu et al. (2010) provide a categorical delineation of greywater as water imbued with a mild level of contamination stemming from human activities, deemed amenable to repurposing following appropriate treatment. According to Shaikh, I. N., & Ahammed, M. M. (2020). The fundamental tenet underpinning domestic greywater reuse revolves around the substitution of a portion or the entirety of non-potable water requirements with reclaimed water. Consequently, the accrued recycled greywater presents a viable resource for applications such as toilet flushing and/or irrigating gardens. In the specific context of the design case, considering a recycling efficiency of 80%, the potential yield of recycled greywater stands at a noteworthy 878.568 Kl per (Table 3).

Table 3. Grey Water Recycling Potential Calculation (Design Case)

	Coefficient	Total Litres/Per Day	Total Litres/Per Year
Grey Water generated (70% of Domestic Use)		3008.796	1098210.54
Grey Water (Recycling) Potential	0.8	2407.0368	878568.432

Landscape design and Xeriscaping In pursuit of heightened efficiency in landscape irrigation, the deliberate design of a 1000 square meter site area is orchestrated to accommodate tree vegetation. This design curtails the volume of necessary irrigation and fosters an augmented biodiversity. As articulated by Özyavuz, A. and Özyavuz, M. (2012), the implementation of a Xeriscape-type landscape featuring indigenous flora has the potential to reduce outdoor water consumption by up to 50 percent, all while preserving the aesthetic quality and allure of the surroundings. This ecological landscaping approach not only aligns with environmental sustainability but also boasts attributes such as minimal upkeep requirements, reduced dependency on fertilizers, and diminished reliance on chemical inputs. Within the confines of the design case, the strategic adoption of xeriscaping endeavors to realize a substantial annual reduction in water consumption, quantified at 7,163.490 Kl, as detailed in Table 4. Furthermore, in a bid to fortify food resilience, the proposal introduces a terrace garden designated for food cultivation, necessitating a corresponding calculation of irrigation demand to ensure a holistic approach to resource management.

Critical Storage In ensuring the operational robustness of a building amid resilience challenges pertaining to water management, it is imperative to extend the infrastructure beyond a primary storage tank. A supplementary storage reservoir, designated as the critical storage tank, assumes a pivotal role in addressing water requisites during times of calamity, characterized by disruptions in transportation services or disruptions in the supply chain. To fortify the building's ability to withstand such exigencies, an auxiliary water storage tank with a volumetric capacity of 13.6 kiloliters is incorporated alongside the primary storage container. Remarkably, this critical reservoir is dimensioned at 1.5 times the daily demand, safeguarding against potential shortfalls in water availability during unforeseen disaster scenarios. It is imperative to note that this critical storage facility operates independently of the previously proposed storage tank intended for rainwater, thus establishing a layered and comprehensive approach to water resilience within the building infrastructure.

Table 4. Landscape Water Demand Calculation

	Area in Sqm	Litres/SqM/Day	Total Litres/Day	Total Litres/Year
Ground Cover (Base Case)	2164	10	2164	7898600
Ground Cover (Xeriscaping)	1164	1	1164	424860
Rooftop Garden (Food Production)	425	2	850	310250
Total Landscape Water Demand				735110

Table 5. Net positive Water Calculations

	Total Litres/Year
Grey water Produced after recycling	878568.432
Flushing Demand	608090
Greywater left after use for flushing	270478.432
Harvested Rainwater	2200800
Landscape Demand	735110
Harvested Rainwater Remained after landscape Use	1736168.432

Net positive Water After Following the strategic mitigation of landscape irrigation and flushing demands through the utilization of recycled greywater and harvested rainwater, an appreciable surplus of rainwater, amounting to 1,371.168 Kl (Table 5), becomes available for allocation. This surplus, endowed with potential, can be directed towards the dual objectives of recharging groundwater reservoirs and, post-filtration, offsetting a segment of the demand for potable water. In periods of calamity, this meticulously filtered rainwater emerges as a pivotal resource, significantly augmenting self-sufficiency by providing a reliable source of portable water. The judicious orchestration of these measures culminates in a commendable 3 days of autonomy during instances of disaster. This temporal resilience underscores the efficacy and foresight embedded in the comprehensive water management approach, wherein surplus rainwater assumes a multifaceted role not only in sustaining landscape and flushing needs but also in fortifying the fundamental access to potable water during critical circumstances.

Energy The base case energy demand for the recognized PHC is 77.048 kWh (EPI – 24.2 kWh/m²/year). To mitigate this demand, strategies involving the use of energy-efficient fixtures are employed, aligning with the sustainability principle of reducing demand as a primary measure as stated by Cotton et al (2021) and Patel et al (2023). In addition, renewable energy sourced from solar panels is integrated to meet both regular and critical demand, particularly for crucial periods. Moreover, supplementary critical energy storage is incorporated as a backup to ensure the continued operation of essential infrastructure during critical times.

Energy-efficient fixtures LEDs and BLDC fans are incorporated into the design case, as they consume less electricity and have a longer lifespan than traditional fixtures. In the calculated demand for the design case, which is 59.208 kWh, there is a 23% reduction from the base case demand of 77.048 kWh for the overall energy demand per day (Table 6).

Critical storage Considering the potential disruption in energy supply during disaster times, along with the crucial energy required to facilitate the functioning of essential infrastructure supporting the primary operations of the Primary Health Center (PHC), an auxiliary storage serving as a backup during challenging times is incorporated. This critical storage demand is calculated by exclusively considering appliances and equipment required to function with continuous power supply during outages. Maintaining the functionality of critical medical devices listed below is of paramount importance. The Critical devices required (watts per day) - Refrigerator-vaccine (1440W), Radio & Phone (30W), Notebook Computer (60W), Fan (5400W), Miscellaneous equipment (2400W), Interior Lighting (9360W), Corridor Lighting (2080W), Security & Pathway lighting (1560W), Table lamp for newborn baby (400W), ECG Machine (1200W), Surgical Suction Machine (180W). The calculated Critical case energy demand is 24.11 kWh per day (Table 6).

Renewable energy Elliott (2000) states that renewable energy is seen as a necessary step toward sustainable energy development, the reduction of the use of fossil fuels, and mitigating climate change. Renewable energy sources, such as solar power, should be harnessed, particularly in regions like Chennai, where solar energy can be readily harvested due to its warm and humid climatic conditions, as per NBC (2016). Solar panels can serve as a reliable source of electricity, ensuring that crucial medical equipment and facilities have continuous power even during grid failures. Solar energy is a clean and renewable source of energy, it produces minimal environmental impact compared to traditional energy sources. Using solar panels can also reduce the carbon footprint and promote environmental sustainability. Solar panels enhance primary healthcare facilities' resilience to climate change impacts, such as extreme weather events and disruptions to traditional energy infrastructure. This will allow maintaining health services during emergencies. Solar power generation

(efficiency - 22.8%, Daylight hours -10.5) is calculated for clear sky conditions as well as days with a cloudy or overcast sky. In the Clear Sky Condition scenario, the average Solar Radiation is 0.45 kWh, and Solar Energy Generated per sqm is 1.0773 kWh. In the Cloudy or Overcast sky scenario, the average Solar Radiation is 0.356 kWh, and Solar Energy Generated per sqm is 0.852 kWh. In both scenarios, an area of 500 sqm for solar energy generation can satisfy the total energy requirement per day (52.208 kWh) and critical storage demand (24.11 kWh) and direct the net positive energy to the on-grid system.

Table 6. Energy demand calculations

Equipment	Quantity	No of hours	Base Case		Design Case	
			W/hour	watts/day	W/hour	watts/day
Refrigerator - vaccine	1	24	60	1440	60	1440
General Purpose Refrigerator	1	24	150	3600	150	3600
Centrifuge	1	4	484	1936	484	1936
Microscope	1	6	40	240	40	240
Blood Chemical analyzer	1	4	88	352	88	352
Hematology Analyzer	1	4	230	920	230	920
CD4 Machine	1	4	200	800	200	800
Radio & Phone	1	2	30	60	30	60
Notebook Computer	1	4	30	120	30	120
Fan	27	12	75	24300	50	16200
Miscellaneous equipment	1	7	100	700	100	700
Interior Lighting	32	15	50	24000	40	19200
Corridor Lighting	8	13	50	5200	40	4160
Security & Pathway lighting	6	13	90	7020	40	3120
Table lamp for newborn baby	1	6	200	1200	200	1200
ECG Machine, ordinary	1	4	1200	4800	1200	4800
Surgical Suction Machine	1	2	180	360	180	360
Water Pump	1	2	-	-	1000	2000
				77048		61208

Net positive Energy After incorporating strategies like reduction through energy efficient fixtures and renewable energy resources from solar power, an energy demand of 61.208 kWh is completely powered by solar power generation and directing 477 kWh of energy to the on-grid system daily. The payback period is the time required to recover the capital cost incurred. In this case, investment in solar power generation through solar panels can bring back the returns with a payback period of 7 years. After storing the net positive energy generated from solar panels during disruption for critical demand, 17 days of autonomy in energy resilience can be achieved.

Fig 3. Graphical representation of rooftop edible landscaping and solar panels.

Food Ira Matuschke and Stefan Kohler (2014) state that food security is a multi-layered concept. The four dimensions of food security are sufficient availability of food, secured access to food, adequate and deed-based utilization of food, and long-term stability of food supply. According to Matthew Solan (2023), Men need 2.4 kcal, and women need 2 kcal daily. Considering the facility’s occupancy is about 90 persons, the daily caloric demand is 198 kcal.

Terrace farming On-site farming can offer a diverse diet to the patients and staff. Access to fresh, locally grown produce enhances the quality of meals, which helps provide nutrition to the occupants even when transportation is disrupted during or after a disaster. The stored produce can sustain the healthcare facility’s operations, especially when external resources are limited. It also contributes to creating green infrastructure on the healthcare facility premises, reducing the environmental impact. Sweet potato, a high-calorie density vegetable, is chosen for cultivation, which can produce 470 kcal caloric value per day in a cultivating area of 100 sqm. Upon using the concept of Agrivoltics, the same area can be

used for both cultivation and solar power generation such that space is optimized along with the benefit of both products (Fig. 3). Suffice annual food requirement can be achieved with an area of 425 sqm on the terrace for food Cultivation, which is enough for feeding the occupants daily and will also act as Food resilience by storing for critical periods. This integration of geaponics for food cultivation with a cultivatable area of 425 sqm achieves 9.5 days of autonomy of food resilience.

Impact Analysis of Base and Design Case

Energy The energy demand is reduced by using energy-efficient fixtures and making the building net positive energy by solar energy generation. Base Case Energy Demand of 77.048 kWh (EPI – 24.2 kWh/m2/year) is reduced in the Design Case to 59.208 kWh (EPI – 18.6 kWh/m2/year) with a reduction of 23.15%. The critical Case Energy requirement is 24.11 kWh (Fig. 4).

Fig 4. Energy demand reduction between base and design case

Water The water demand is reduced by using low-flow fixtures, recycling greywater for flushing demand, and harvesting rainwater to make the building’s net water positive. The landscape demand is reduced to 15% using xeriscaping and efficient landscape design. All these strategies have resulted in an energy demand reduction of 36.85%, where the Base Case water demand of 11373.4 Kl is reduced in the Design Case to 3294.446 Kl (Fig. 5).

Fig 5. Water demand reduction between base and design case.

Food The required daily caloric intake for occupants, amounting to 198 Kcal per day, is achieved by integrating geaponics in terrace farming, covering a cultivating area of 425 sqm. This integration enhances food resilience, mitigates the heat island effect, and improves biodiversity on the site. With this strategic approach, a remarkable 9.5 days of autonomy in food resilience is attained, ensuring food provision during the disaster period.

Environmental Impact Using renewable power sources represents an environmentally friendly approach that significantly reduces the carbon footprint compared to traditional energy production. Simultaneously, strategies such as reducing water demand, recycling greywater, and rainwater harvesting decrease reliance on groundwater and align with sustainability principles of reduction, reusing, and recycling. Implementing practices like terrace farming and incorporating green spaces effectively mitigates the impact of urban heat islands, providing multifaceted environmental advantages. These strategies demonstrate improvements in air quality, temperature regulation, and the promotion of biodiversity and mitigate sick building syndrome. Additionally, integrating energy-efficient fixtures, such as LEDs, contributes to a minimal environmental footprint. This comprehensive and integrated approach, encompassing Food, Energy, and Water systems, collectively diminishes the overall environmental impact.

Conclusion

The primary objective of this paper is to comprehensively comprehend and apply strategies within the realm of FEW

systems, with a specific focus on bolstering the resilience of critical infrastructure, particularly healthcare centers. This methodological approach facilitates a nuanced exploration of the quantitative feasibility and efficacy of these strategies, thereby providing a replicable blueprint for similar scenarios aiming to enhance the resilience of analogous structures. These strategies are meticulously identified and aligned with the cardinal principles of Reduction, Reuse/Recycle, and Renewal. In the sphere of energy management, a noteworthy reduction of 23% in consumption is achieved in the design case through the strategic incorporation of efficient fixtures such as LEDs and BLDC Fans. The installation of solar panels further propels the paradigm toward net positive energy, exhibiting a commendable payback period of 7 years. Remarkably, the design case attains a significant milestone in energy resilience, boasting an impressive 17 days of autonomy. Water demand, too, undergoes a transformative reduction of 36.85%, courtesy of the integration of low-flow fixtures, while achieving a net positive water scenario through the judicious implementation of rainwater harvesting, xeriscaping, and greywater recycling. The collective impact of these strategies manifests in a substantial 3 days of water autonomy. Agrivoltics, as a strategic space optimization measure, seamlessly integrates solar power generation and food cultivation, yielding a daily produce that sustains food requirements for an impressive 9.5 days, thus establishing a resilient autonomy period of equal duration. This integrated approach towards resilience manifests in a discernible mitigation of environmental impact, encompassing reductions in carbon footprint, pollution, and heat island effect. Notably, these outcomes align intricately with the stringent standards set forth by the RELi rating system, particularly in safeguarding critical infrastructure. Therefore, this study provides a comprehensive understanding of enhancing building resilience and serves as a practical and innovative model for architects and builders confronted with analogous challenges in the contemporary landscape. Its insights and solutions are particularly valuable for regions prone to disasters, offering a forward-thinking framework for sustainable and resilient development.

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